

Green Wave: Explaining the Appeal
of the Green Party among Young
British Voters

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*Freedom, Courage,
Truth.*

Executive Summary

The rise of the Green Party under its radical new leader Zack Polanski, its resounding victory in the Gorton and Denton by-election and its astounding support level among younger voters is one of the big new stories in British politics.

This report fields a new survey to investigate why the Green Party appeals so strongly to young voters. The survey oversamples younger and left-leaning voters to explore their worldview and voting patterns. Beyond this, the study considers what the rise of the new Green vote portends for the next election and the long-term future of British politics.

The report finds that young people are considerably more likely than their elders to identify as far left, and that young leftists are far more inclined to vote Green than older leftists. 'Generation Woke' does a better job of explaining young leftism than 'Generation Rent.' That is, cultural progressive attitudes such as endorsing transwomen in women's sports help to explain young leftism. Materialist concerns such as being unable to afford a house or endorsing higher taxes and spending are less prominent. While the cost of living is the most important issue for young people, it is also a top issue for most voters and therefore a competence question which is less party-positional. Cultural issues are lower-ranked in importance but more positional and closely associated with strong left-wing ideology, which is the most important correlate of Green voting.

Young leftists are more Green-inclined not just because they are more left-wing but because they have not formed attachments to Labour the way older leftists have and are more likely to view the ruling party as responsible for the country's problems. We see something similar on the right in other countries where younger voters are more likely than their elders to vote for national populists over established conservatives.

While the Green Party is unlikely to win the next election, cohort change in the coming decades could carry them toward the centre of power. By 2036 or 2046 the left-wing cast of Britain's younger electorate may well alter the

country's natural party of government from a right-wing party, as has been the case in the past, to a left-wing one, as in Canada.

Key Findings:

Voting

- In national representative surveys, nearly half of voters under age 25 intend to vote Green
- In my survey, 57 percent of left-wing voters aged 18-35 intend to vote Green, three times the 17 percent of left-wing voters over 50 who said they would do so
- The 18-25 age group is more right-leaning than the 26-35 age group, but also more likely, by 46-35, to support the Greens
- Zack Polanski's personal popularity does not explain the Green's disproportionate appeal to young people: he is somewhat more popular among older Green voters than among younger Green voters

Ideology

- The 18-35s are three times more likely to identify as far left than older voters
- The 18-35s are six times more likely to support transwomen entering women's sporting competitions as Britons over 35
- 6 in 10 Green voters under 35 support transwomen in women's sporting competitions compared to 25 percent of young Labour voters and 2 percent of young Reform voters the same age
- 71 percent of left-wing identifiers over 50 favour increased taxes and spending compared to 45 percent of left-wing identifiers aged 18-35
- Housing affordability is more important for young voters than older voters but still ranks well below the NHS on young voters' list of priorities
- Green voters do not care more about housing affordability and generational difficulty in buying a house than other voters. Housing is a similarly-ranked issue for young Green, Labour and Reform voters
- Single, poor or those who are not in work are no more likely to vote Green than other voters
- Cost of living is a leading issue for 69 percent of young non-Green voters, but a top issue for 85 percent of young Green voters, marking the one important materialist difference between Labour and Green voters.

- Left-wing voters care a lot less about immigration, and more about the cost of living, than right-wing voters
- Young left-wing voters are more concerned about crime than older left-wing voters

Tactical Voting

- Voters for left-wing parties are more likely than voters for right-wing parties to say that they are uncertain who is the frontrunning party in their constituency, or to say that the margin will be extremely close. This benefits Reform
- Left party voters are about 15 points more willing to switch to Labour to keep Reform out than Tory voters are to switch to Reform to keep Labour out. This benefits Labour, if they remain the leading left party
- The question of who benefits from tactical voting will depend on whether the Reform-Tory polling lead or Labour-Green lead is larger, in order to send a clearer signal to tactical voters. Currently this benefits Reform
- Whether tactical voting benefits Reform or Labour will turn on the balance of these conflicting tendencies

The [victory](#) of the Green Party's Hannah Spencer in the Gorton and Denton riding in Greater Manchester, one of the most left-leaning constituencies in the country, on 27 February 2026, came as a profound shock to Labour. The Greens won 41 percent against just 25 percent for Labour and 29 percent for Reform. The Conservatives and Liberal Democrats each polled at under 2 percent, failing to reach the threshold needed to win back their deposit.¹

In a subsequent [poll](#), commissioned by Sky News, YouGov reported that Green support had risen to 21 percent, placing them ahead of Labour in second place, only a few points back of Reform. Strikingly, Green was the top choice among the under-50s, reaching half the vote among the under-25s. Young voters have always been the Greens' friendliest segment, but as Figure 1 illustrates, the rate of Green support among the under-25s more than doubled between August 2025 and March 2026.

The same doubling occurred in the general population, but the magnitude of current young support stands out. Notice as well that there is no evidence of a Reform proclivity among Britain's younger voters – this is not simply a populist response against the mainstream parties but a clear shift toward a specifically left populism. Reform also increased its vote share in recent years, but its surge took place from late 2023 to mid 2025, after which it has been stable.

Figure 1

Source: YouGov vote intention [tracker](#), accessed 9 March 2026.

This report focuses on the rise of the Greens, especially among young people. The leading explanations for this

¹ 'Green Party wins Gorton and Denton by-election, pushing Labour into third place,' BBC, 27 February, 2026

new development in British politics are twofold. First, the *materialist* claim that the young are revolting because they are struggling to buy a house and meet the high costs of living. Second, the *culturalist* argument that progressive beliefs around race, gender and sexuality (or adjacent issues) account for young people's tilt toward the cultural radicalism of Zack Polanski. Polanski, for instance, favours transwomen accessing women's spaces and is relaxed about immigration and hard drug legalisation.

Generation Rent or Generation Woke?

Are the young flocking to Polanski or his by-election star Hannah Spencer because they are, in Patrick West's view, [emotionally captivated](#) by the empathetic vibe emoted by the Greens: 'Spencer's victory speech exposed the vacuity of their 'kind politics', and indeed the entire babyish belief that the world would be perfect if only everyone would stop being so horrid.'² This is the culturalist Generation Woke hypothesis.

Or is because they are struggling? Consider this [explanation](#) on X by respondent 'Tommy P' who rejects the culturalist thesis: 'Is it more plausible that a generation suddenly became stupid because of education or a generation locked out of home ownership, facing £1,000+ rents, stagnant pay....' This is the materialist Generation Rent argument.

Survey Design

To find out which theory better fits the facts, I conducted a survey of 385 British voters on the [Prolific](#) survey platform on 5 March 2026. This is a convenience sample that is not designed or weighted to be representative as this is not required for this kind of analysis. The site's demographic leans young and left, which is ideal for the group I wanted to capture. 55 percent of the sample voted Labour or Green in 2024 compared to just 19 percent for Tory or Reform. Excluding nonvoters, 42 percent of those under-35 said they would vote for Polanski if an election were held tomorrow.

Voting Trends among Young People

What correlates with intending to voting Green? Age is by far the strongest demographic predictor in the Prolific survey: 46 percent of those 25 and under support Polanski compared to 5 percent of the over-55s.

The young female effect is also noticeable. John Burn-Murdoch has [summarised](#) data from several surveys on

² West, Patrick, 'The real reason Greens are gaining ground,' *Spectator*, 6 March 2026.

the gender gap in voting among young people in several western countries.³ I find the same pattern in this data, even as the sample size is too small to find a significant age-sex interaction effect. Among the 18-25s, the female-to-male advantage for Polanski is 56-30, for the 26-35s it is 44-25 and among the 36-45s it is 27-15. By contrast, there is no Green gender gap among the over-45s, which suggests the political gender gap is a young adult phenomenon.

Younger voters in Britain are significantly more likely to vote for a left-wing party (Labour, Liberal Democrat, Green, SNP, Plaid Cymru) than older voters. This has been especially true for a decade since Brexit. Data from the British Election Study (BES) in Figure 2 shows that an age gap of 10-20 points between the 18-25s and 65+ voters in voting Conservative first began to emerge in the 2010s. It subsequently widened to 35-40 points during the post-Brexit elections of 2017 and 2019. The apparent convergence to 20 points in the 2020s largely reflects the Tories declining popularity among older voters rather than its revival among young voters.

Figure 2

Source: British Election Study (BES) 1964-2024, and YouGov 2026.

The Prolific sample, which leans left of the electorate as a whole, nevertheless reflects Britain's current political age gradient. Figure 3 shows that younger voters opt for the Green Party more than middle-aged and older voters. This is partly because older voters are more likely to vote for right-wing parties like Reform or the Tories, but also because older left-wing voters prefer Labour to the Greens. Thus among voters under 36, the Greens

³ Burn-Murdoch, John, 'A new global gender divide is emerging,' *Financial Times*, 26 January 2024.

edge Labour 37-19 while among those over 45, Labour has a 24-12 advantage. The youngest age group is slightly more right-leaning than those 26-35 but tilts Green over Labour by a whopping 46-12! Ideology is not a sufficient explanation for the rise of Green. Rather, something about being young, independent of being left-wing, also explains Green's appeal.

Figure 3

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=385.

Political Ideology and Issue Attitudes

Political scientists often think about voting and partisanship as being partly independent of personal ideology, which in turn is somewhat independent of attitudes to individual issues.⁴ In more polarized societies like America, issues, ideology, partisanship and voting tend to overlap a great deal.⁵ But in Britain, party polarization, the sorting of ideology with party, the matching of issues to ideology and the politicization of society is less intense.

Are young people more Green because they are more left? Having examined voting patterns by age, I next consider the relationship between age and ideology. When it comes to how people identify their political beliefs on a 5-point scale from 'very left-wing' to 'very right-wing', differences are present by age, but the picture differs somewhat from the age pattern for vote.

⁴ University of Michigan. Survey Research Center. and A. Campbell (1964). *The American voter, an abridgment*. New York., Wiley.
⁵ Iyengar, S., et al. (2019). "The origins and consequences of affective polarization in the United States." *Annual Review of Political Science* 22: 129-146.

Figure 4 shows that around 20 percent of voters under 35 identify as right-wing, considerably less than the 40 percent among those over 55. Yet, interestingly, the 26-35s identify as further left than the 18-25s even as the youngest cohort leans most strongly toward the Greens. zoomers (i.e. 18-25s) are more conservative yet more Green than younger millennials (i.e. aged 26-35). Having said this, the far left share of the youngest age group is about the same as it is among the 26-35s. Together, the 18-35s have a significantly higher share of far leftists (22-23 percent) compared to those over age 35 (6-9 percent).

Figure 4

Issue Attitudes

Having examined the age structure of voting and ideology, I next move to examine age breaks on specific issue positions across a series of eight questions. The first group of questions taps people's views on culturally-inflected issues:

1. **Thinking about political correctness, are you generally in favour of it (it protects against discrimination), or against it (it stifles freedom of speech)?** [In favour (it protects against discrimination) / Against (it stifles free speech)/ Don't know]
2. **Generally speaking, should transwomen (those born male who now identify as female) be permitted to compete in women's sporting competitions?** [Yes/No/Don't know]
3. **What is your view on the right immigration level for Britain?** [All who wish to should be able to come/Increase a lot/ Increase a little/ Remain the same/ Reduce a little/Reduce a lot/ Cut to zero/Don't know]

The next item measures classic left-right economic attitudes:

4. **Generally speaking, would you prefer the government to...**[Increase taxes and spend more on public services/ Keep taxes and spending about the same/ Cut taxes and spend less on public services/ Don't know]

The subsequent question zeroes in on empathy for the needy rather than resentment of the rich or support for socialism, even as it touches on the latter:

5. **Thinking about eligibility criteria for disability benefits, do you think the criteria are too strict, not strict enough, or about right?** [Much too strict/ A bit too strict/ About right/ A bit too loose/ Much too loose/ Don't know]

This is followed by two questions on generational housing fairness:

6. **Do you think house prices in Britain should generally be lower, higher, or about the same as they are now?** [Much lower/ A little lower/ About the same as now/ A little higher/ Much higher]
7. **Do you think today's young people have worse opportunities to buy a home than previous generations?** [Strongly agree/ Agree/Neither agree nor disagree/ Disagree/ Strongly disagree]

And finally a traditional 'green' question on action on climate change:

8. **To what extent do you support or oppose the government's commitment to cutting carbon emissions to net zero by 2050?** [Strongly support/ Tend to support/ Tend to oppose/ Strongly oppose/ Don't know]

Figure 5 dichotomizes the items so the answers can be more easily grasped and compared across age groups.

The figure only examines results for the 234 of 385 total respondents who reported that they would vote for a left-wing party. This thereby screens out the fact that older voters are more right-leaning, allowing me to focus squarely on intra-left dynamics. To wit, the chart analyzes whether the issue attitudes of older and younger left party voters are similar.

This turns out to be largely the case.

The first point to observe is the relative lack of an age gradient across age bars for most of the questions. On

identifying as left-wing, housing, net zero, viewing disability eligibility criteria as too strict and immigration attitudes, we see no consistent age slopes even as there are modest differences. When it comes to support for political correctness (minority protection over free speech), left voters over 55 are cooler than left voters under 55, but there is no consistent age pattern.

The lack of an age gradient in the above questions is especially important in view of noise in the data due to sampling error (i.e. small sample size) and arbitrary cutoffs in the age brackets. Statistical analysis, which follows, will help to test for a robust age pattern.

Two issues stand out visually as having a more consistent age gradient: a) older left party voters are more likely to favour taxing and spending than younger left party voters; and b) left party voters 35 and under are much more likely to say that transwomen should access women’s sports than left party voters over age 35. This intimates that the meaning of leftism is more materialist for older left voters and more culturally ‘woke’ for younger left voters.

Having said this, it is worth reiterating that middle-aged left voters (36-55) are as strongly pro-political correctness as younger millennials and zoomers; only left voters over 55 have a consistently more Old Left (i.e. material socialist yet culturally more conservative) attitude profile.

Figure 5

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=234 left party voters.

This reinforces copious evidence from YouGov tracker polls on attitudes to race, gender and sexuality, and my [own survey work](#) in 2021 which showed that young Britons are more likely to adopt the ‘woke’ position on culture wars issues.⁶ This is especially true for the most radical stances, such as assigning white pupils the status of privileged in class, removing Churchill’s statue or cancelling J.K. Rowling. Figure 6 shows the size of the age effect on various culture war attitudes after controlling for ideology and other demographic factors.

Figure 6

Source: YouGov survey data from Kaufmann, E., ‘The Politics of the Culture Wars in Contemporary Britain,’ *Policy Exchange*, 21 November 2022.

As Figure 7 shows, the same study found that age was about as important as left-right ideology in predicting a person’s position on questions of free speech (i.e. is it wrong to cancel someone for offensive words on race, gender or sexuality) and on trans issues. Age was also an important predictor of attitudes toward removing or retaining statues of historical figures such as David Hume and Winston Churchill who have been accused of racism by the left.

⁶ Kaufmann, E., ‘The Politics of the Culture Wars in Contemporary Britain,’ *Policy Exchange*, 21 November, 2022.

Figure 7

Source: YouGov survey data from Kaufmann, E., 'The Politics of the Culture Wars in Contemporary Britain,' *Policy Exchange*, 21 November 2022.

Issue Salience

An early question in the survey probed issue *salience* – the relative priority of particular issues to respondents regardless of their attitudes toward those issues. The question reads, 'Which of the following do you think is the most important issue facing Britain today? (please rank, with 1 as most important)'. The 13 issues listed included: defence / national security, immigration, economy, welfare and benefits, NHS / healthcare, crime, taxes and government spending, environment / climate change, transport and infrastructure, cost of living, education / student debt, housing affordability / house prices and other.

The lower the number, the more important the issue for an individual, thus 1 is a person's top-ranked issue.

Figure 8 displays the average issue ranking by age category in the Prolific survey, with lower average bars more important than higher ones. The presentation of issue bars is sorted by age gap as calculated by the difference between the 18-35s and 55-plus amalgamated age groups. The sets of bars with bigger age gaps are at the left and right ends of the chart.

Older voters rank defence, immigration and the economy more highly than younger voters. Younger voters rank cost of living (slightly), education/student debt and housing affordability more highly than older voters. The 18-25s, for instance, rank housing affordability as their 5th most important issue on average (5.3), while the 65 and over group rank it between their 7th and 8th most important (7.4).

Having said this, the similarities are more important than the differences: cost of living, NHS/ healthcare and the

economy rank as the highest concerns (average positions 3-5). Infrastructure and education/student debt emerge as less important than other issues (average positions 7-9).

Figure 8

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=385.

Looking at the same chart by political ideology rather than age in Figure 9 reveals that right-wing respondents care more about immigration, defence, crime and taxation than the left. We see a very wide 6-point ideological difference over the prioritization of immigration, ranked 9th most important by left-wing respondents and 3rd most important by right-wing respondents. There is also a 3-point difference on the importance of defence, and 1-point gaps on crime and taxing/spending. At the other end of the chart, left identifiers care 1.5-2 points more about climate change, the cost of living, the NHS, Housing affordability and education/ student debt than right identifiers. There is little ideological divide on the importance of the economy and infrastructure.

Figure 9

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=385.

The last chart, like Figure 8, focuses on the salience of issues by age, but this time the chart is restricted to left party voters. This thereby controls for the fact that young people are more left-wing than older voters. The chart is again sorted by the size of the age gap on each particular issue.

Figure 10 shows that older left party voters care a little over 1 point more about the economy than left voters aged 18-35. At the other end of the scale, the youngest left party voters are around 1 point more concerned about crime than the oldest left voters and 2 points more worried about housing affordability. There are no other consistent age differences: among everyone who votes for a left party, infrastructure and immigration rank low, while taxing/spending and welfare/benefits rank in the middle. Cost of living is the leading issue, just ahead of the NHS, with housing affordability a middling concern.

This analysis shows that within the left-wing coalition there are only modest age differences in the priorities accorded to different issues, and then only on a few questions. Housing costs matter to young people more than the old, but that the issue is not top-ranking – even among younger voters. Cost of living is the top issue for younger voters, but is also the leading issue among older voters. That is, cost of living is a ‘valence’ or competence issue that all agree on rather than a generational issue.⁷

⁷ Clarke, H. D. (2009). *Performance politics and the British voter*, Cambridge University Press.

Counterintuitively, young people care a lot more about the NHS than house prices: the 18-25s rank the NHS as their third most important issue, followed closely by cost of living, with housing ranking fifth. This speaks to the importance of sociotropic (caring about societal issues in general) over egotropic (caring about issues that affect oneself) concerns in public opinion and electoral behaviour.⁸

Figure 10

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=234 left party voters.

We have seen that young people are considerably more likely to vote for the Green Party than older voters. The young are also more left-wing ideologically, though this peaks in the 26-35 age group. On issues, young people are more concerned about housing affordability and student debt than older voters but still do not rank these concerns as highly as cost of living, the NHS and the economy. Young left party voters are much more likely to support the right of transwomen to enter women's sporting competitions than older left party voters while older left voters are more socialist on taxing and spending than their younger counterparts.

Identifying Correlates of Political Ideology and Vote Choice

Models can help to smooth out random fluctuations in the data to get at underlying relationships. In order to test which factors are associated with the outcomes of interest while controlling for confounding explanations, I use a

⁸ Kinder, D. R. and D. R. Kiewiet (1979). "Economic discontent and political behavior: The role of personal grievances and collective economic judgments in congressional voting." *American Journal of Political Science*: 495-527.

3-stage regression modelling strategy. The first stage examines how age affects issue attitudes, the second how age affects ideology, and the third how age and ideology interact to shape Green voting. I am interested in understanding whether age dynamics are important at the issue stage, the ideology stage, the voting stage or at all stages.

Beginning with the two issue models in Figure 11, the first examines the interaction of age and ideology on support for transwomen entering women's sports, and the second on support for higher taxes and spending. All this controlling for a respondent's gender, sexuality, education and income.

The two graphs in Figure 11 tell different stories that chime with the earlier visual analysis of Figures 8-10.

Beginning with the left chart, on views on transwomen in women's sports, young leftists stand out from old leftists in supporting transwomen in women's sports while centrists and conservatives of all ages remain heavily opposed.

By contrast, when it comes to increasing taxing and spending, older voters are more socialist than younger voters. This age gradient holds within left, centre and right ideological bands whereas for trans the age effect only obtained among those identifying as left-wing.

Here is some evidence for the existence of a more materialist old left and more culturalist young left. The caveat is that when we take the political correctness and immigration questions into consideration, it is really the left-wing over-55s that stand out as more socialist on taxes and spending while being relatively conservative on cultural questions. The 36-54s are not as culturally radical as the 18-35s but embody some identity-based New Left ideas (as with support for political correctness and moderate support for the transactivist position).

Figure 11 Models of Issue Attitudes, by Ideology and Age

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2025. N = 385. $R^2 = .381$ for trans model and $.124$ for tax/spend model (OLS used to avoid dropping data points). Controls for gender, income, education and sexual orientation. Age x ideology interactions only significant for trans, not for taxes and spending.

Moving from the age pattern on issues to the relationship of age with ideology, a model predicting a person's ideology on a 5-point scale is presented in Figure 12. Answers to both the immigration and material questions (taxing/spending, importance of cost of living) are strongly associated with ideology. The model also shows that older respondents lean right of younger respondents. However, controlling for attitudes to taxing and spending, net zero, immigration, and transwomen in sports; as well as the salience of immigration and the cost of living to a respondent, age falls just below statistical significance. When I interact age with attitudes, the age main effect disappears entirely. Thus much of the age-ideology relationship (i.e. young people identifying as more left) is accounted for by younger voters' more leftist issue attitudes.

In testing the model, the issue attitudes that most affected the coefficient for age were the trans issue followed by the importance of cost of living. Young people differ from the old most on transwomen in women's sports and the importance of cost of living. Thus while both culturalist and material concerns matter when explaining age gaps in political beliefs, there is more support for the culturalist thesis. A similar pattern emerges when focusing

on far left identification as the outcome measure.

Earlier, we saw that age and ideology combined to predict issue positions on trans. Thus it is not surprising that I find an interaction between age and views on the trans-in-sports question in the ideology model, such that young people who are pro-transwomen in women's sports are especially likely to identify as far left compared to younger individuals who oppose the transactivist position. Among older voters, trans makes less of a difference to a person's ideology (recall that few older leftists hold the transactivist position). Thus culture war questions appear to matter more for young people's ideological identity than older people's ideology. No other interactions – such as age and views on taxation - were significant in predicting a person's ideology (note that Figure 12 does not show the age interactions).

Figure 12

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=341. $R^2=.463$. + $p<.1$; * $p<.05$; ** $p<.01$; *** $p<.001$.

One takeaway thus far is that the trans issue has a much clearer age profile than questions around housing. The black bars in Figure 13 below show that among the under-35s, there is only a modest difference in the share of Green (32 percent), Labour (27 percent) and Reform voters who picked housing as a top-3 issue from a list of 13. Only the handful of younger Tory voters felt housing was of less importance. This said, there is a more of a difference between Green and the others on the importance of cost of living, with 85 percent of young Green voters ranking this issue in their top 3 compared to 50-63 percent of other major party voters the same age. What is most striking, however, is that when asked whether transwomen (those born male who identify as

women) should be permitted to enter women’s sporting competitions, 60 percent of younger Green voters said yes, in line with Zack Polanski’s views. This compares with 25 percent of Labour voters, 8 percent of Tory voters, and 2 percent of Reform voters the same age. The Greens stand out far more on cultural issues than on housing or even cost of living. The ideological gradient is very powerful on trans, but weaker on the more material issues. This said, dissatisfaction with Labour on cost of living may be important in turning some young leftist voters off Labour and toward the Greens.

Figure 13

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=139 voters aged 18-35.

Narrowing the dataset to those who voted for a left-wing party in 2024, I next sought to create a model of Green Party voting within the left. Figure 14 shows that more left ideology, being younger, caring less about the economy and immigration and more about net zero, and believing disability benefits criteria are too strict are the best predictors of which 2024 left voter intends to vote Green. Bisexuals and homosexuals are also significantly more likely to vote Green than heterosexuals. Education, income and gender are not significant predictors.

Figure 14

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=262. $R^2=.323$. * $p<.05$; ** $p<.01$; *** $p<.001$.

These findings echo those of larger recent surveys, such as that from 38 Degrees/Persuasion UK, which find that 2024 Labour voters intending to vote Reform care a lot more about immigration than those intending to vote Labour or Green.

For instance, Figure 15 shows that 55 percent of Labour-to-Reform switchers say immigration is one of the three most important issues facing Britain compared to only 10 percent of Labour-to-Green switchers and 18 percent of consistent Labour voters. By contrast there is almost no difference between these sets of voters on the importance of cost of living. Housing ranks much lower, and exhibits only modest differences by intended vote. These issues matter greatly, but do not decide vote choice.

While the cost of living is the most important issue for young people, it is also a top issue for older voters and is therefore a competence question which is less party-positional. Cultural issues are lower-ranked in importance but more positional and closely associated with ideology, which is the most important correlate of voting.

Elsewhere in the 38 Degrees/Persuasion study, those who switch to Green are much more likely (11 percent) to say they switched because Labour is too right-wing than Labour-Reform switchers are to say they switched because Labour is too left-wing. New Green voters also mentioned 'identity politics, wokeness and handling of

trans issues' (5 percent) and Gaza (7 percent) as reasons for deserting Labour while these essentially went unmentioned by Labour-to-Reform switchers. More broadly, 48 percent of those moving from Labour to Green say Labour is too right-wing while just 29 percent of those moving from Labour to Reform or the Tories said Labour was too left-wing. Instead, right switchers mainly complain about competence issues and immigration. There is thus an asymmetry in the reasons for switching, with left switchers more motivated by ideology.⁹

Figure 15

Source: Akehurst, Steve, 'Revolt on the left: Getting to know Labour's 'progressive defectors'', 38

⁹ Akehurst, Steve, 'Revolt on the left: Getting to know Labour's 'progressive defectors'', 38 *Degrees/Persuasion UK*, March 2026, pp. 30-31.

Ideology matters more for Labour voters who switch to the Greens than to Reform or the Tories, but I find an important additional effect involving an interaction between age and ideology. Very left-wing young people are especially likely to vote Green compared to very left-wing older people. Figure 16 shows the results of a model that controls for the suite of variables in my survey used in the model in Figure 14.

The predicted probabilities chart generated from the model reveals that a 20 year-old very left-wing respondent has a .91 chance of voting Green compared to a .14 likelihood of voting Green for an 80 year-old very left voter. For those on the slight left, the probability falls from .49 to .03 as we move from a 20 year-old to an 80 year-old. Centre and right-leaning voters are unlikely to vote Green at any age.¹⁰

Figure 16

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=366. R²=.342. Age x ideology interactions significant at p<.01 level. Controls for gender, sexual orientation, income, education, attitudes to disability benefits and net zero, and importance of immigration, the economy and cost of living.

Why are young leftists much keener on the Greens than older leftists? Zack Polanski's favourability rating is

¹⁰ Note that these models include those who did not vote for a left party in 2024.

obviously highly correlated with the intention to vote Green, but when his leader rating is excluded from the model, the impact of age on the Green vote actually goes down rather than up the way it would if he were the reason for a strong young Green vote. The age interaction with Polanski's rating is also not significant. In fact, Figure 17 shows that among Green voters Polanski is if anything slightly less popular among younger than older people. Thus we can rule out the youthful appeal or charisma of Polanski as the reason for young people backing the party at higher rates than older people. Instead, the stronger explanation is that young leftists are more attuned to certain issues (trans, cost of living) than the old, which Green is successfully plugging into, and are less attached to Labour.¹¹ Labour also happens to be in power, and is thus more easily fingered by young people as the source of the country's problems.

Figure 17

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=90 Green voters.

Putting it all together in the flow diagram in Figure 18, we see that age affects Green voting via issue attitudes and salience, which predicts leftist sentiment. Age then interacts with leftist sentiment to predict Green voting.

¹¹ Kriesi, H., Grande, E., Lachat, R., Dolezal, M., Bornschieer, S., & Frey, T. (2008). *West European Politics in the Age of Globalization*. Cambridge University Press; Norris, P. (2005). *Radical Right: Voters and Parties in the Electoral Market*. Cambridge University Press.

Figure 18 Flow Diagram of Age and Green Voting

Vote Switching and Tactical Voting

The final aspect of this report examines vote switching and the potential for tactical voting, which could be important given the finely-balanced multi-party competition that characterizes the British electorate of today. Current polling suggests that there is considerable movement within the left bloc between Labour and Green, Liberal Democrat or Plaid/SNP. In the right bloc, we see shifts between Reform and Conservative.

In late 2025, Electoral Calculus identified a large ‘anti-Reform’ tactical vote, with over a third (38 percent) of Labour supporters willing to vote Conservative in seats where the Tories were the only party capable of beating Reform. This high level of ‘switching willingness’ was projected to cost Reform over 60 seats, potentially turning a projected outright majority into a hung parliament. The research also showed that two-thirds of Green and Liberal Democrat voters remained willing to back Labour tactically in close races against Reform or the Conservatives. This could limit Green voting in constituencies where Labour is viewed as the frontrunner.

Alongside polling from More in Common, research identified a significant ‘asymmetry of coordination’ between the UK’s left and right voting blocs. The left-leaning electorate (Labour, Liberal Democrats, and Greens) demonstrated a higher willingness to vote tactically, driven by a unified anti-Reform sentiment. Approximately 61–64 percent of Labour and Green supporters expressed a readiness to switch their vote to block a Reform UK victory, with over 75 percent of Labour voters willing to back a Lib Dem or Green candidate if they were the

better-placed challenger.

Conversely, these studies found that the right-wing bloc remains significantly more fragmented and less willing to engage in reciprocal tactical voting. While Reform UK has surged in the polls, only about 38 percent of its supporters are willing to vote tactically for the Conservatives. While Reform voters are somewhat open to backing the Tories to stop the left, a significant portion of the Conservative base remains resistant to backing Reform, with many preferring to abstain or even switch to Labour rather than see a Reform breakthrough.¹²

The impact of this disparity is most visible in anti-Reform coordination. In a historic shift for 2025, over a third (38 percent) of Labour voters indicated they would even vote Conservative in specific seats where the Tories were the only viable alternative to a Reform win. This high degree of strategic flexibility on the left significantly lowers the seat-conversion rate for Reform UK and could potentially prevent them from securing a majority despite reaching a majority-level vote share in the low 30s.

In my Prolific data, I similarly find evidence for a left-right asymmetry in willingness to tactically vote, albeit with a somewhat smaller differential than that reported by Electoral Calculus and More in Common. Figure 19 illustrates that 57 percent of those who would vote Reform as their first choice put the Conservatives as their second choice while just 42 percent of Tories named Reform as their second option. Left parties, by contrast, give almost all of their second choice votes (90 percent or more) to other left parties – even as this is distributed among several parties. Liberal Democrats emerge as disproportionately benefiting from second choice votes, but, given the electoral realities in most constituencies, will be unlikely to benefit from tactical voting.

In a separate question asking about willingness to tactically vote, 65 percent of left party voters say they would tactically vote to keep Reform out while 50 percent of right party voters say they would do the same to keep Labour out (I did not ask about keeping the Greens out).

¹² Electoral Calculus / Find Out Now (2025). 'Tactical Voting 2025: Analysis of Switching Willingness in the UK Population,' September 24, 2025. [www.electoralcalculus.co.uk]; More in Common (2025). 'September MRP: Modelling Fragmentation and Tactical Coordination in British Politics,' September 28, 2025. [www.moreincommon.org.uk]

Figure 19 First and Second Choice Vote Intention

Source: Prolific, 6 March 2026. N=385. Sankey diagram via Flourish.¹³

In March 2026, 38 Degrees/Persuasion UK likewise found that Labour could win back many of its voters who have moved to other left parties. While Labour voters who have switched to Reform or the Tories are less likely to be persuaded to return to the fold (only around 25 percent were open to doing so), 60 percent of those who have moved to a left-wing alternative were open to switching back to Labour.¹⁴ Should Labour emerge as the clear frontrunner in most constituencies, this suggests that tactical voting may help to limit Reform’s success. Leader favourability ratings over time, shown in Figure 20, continue to report a ceiling for Nigel Farage despite Reform’s lead in the polls. This is rooted in left party voters’ high disapproval, with a majority willing to tactically vote against Farage. Zack Polanski, meanwhile, enjoys relatively high ratings alongside Ed Davey of the Liberal Democrats. In addition, as we have seen, Conservative voters (an important number of whom voted Remain in the 2016 referendum on leaving the EU) are more lukewarm toward Reform than left party voters tend to be toward each other. Could Farage’s vote ceiling limit Reform’s potential to reach majority territory?

¹³ Diagram publicly available at: <https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/27988195/>

¹⁴ Akehurst et. al. 2026, p. 34.

Figure 20

The results of the Caerphilly and Gorton and Denton by-elections favoured left bloc parties (Plaid Cymru on 47 percent and Green on 41 percent). Yet, in the 2025 local council elections, Reform won 41 percent of seats contested. While left bloc voters are more motivated to vote tactically to keep Reform out than right bloc voters are to keep Labour out, there are countervailing forces which may advantage Reform. Two dynamics which could work against left bloc tactical voting are that a) many constituencies could feature close races with multiple parties claiming to be the frontrunner, and b) Reform may be more comfortably in front of the Conservatives in many constituencies than Labour, Green or Lib Dem in their stronger constituencies.

In my Prolific data, I compared uncertainty levels about which party was locally strongest between a) right voters living in seats they expect to be won by a left-wing party, and b) left voters living in seats they expect the right to win. Uncertainty (don't know plus those who expected an 'extremely close margin') was higher, at 21 percent, among left voters in seats where a right party was expected to win than among right voters in left-leaning seats, where only 13 percent weren't sure or expected a close contest. Across all types of seats the difference was smaller, at 25 percent among left voters versus 20 percent among right voters. Thus the relatively even spread of votes among the parties compared to the pre-2024 situation of relative two-party dominance is such that Reform is likely to gain an advantage in tactical voting that may offset left-right tactical switching asymmetry.

This of course assumes current polling and no formal electoral pacts.

Conclusion

This investigation into the role of age in recent Green Party support has generated two main explanatory pathways. First, young people are more left-wing than older people, stemming in considerable measure from their more progressive attitudes on cultural questions such as the trans issue and their greater concern over the cost of living. This makes the young more willing to vote Green. When it comes to comparing the culturalist and materialist theses, it is noticeable that housing ranks relatively low on young people's priority list of the problems facing Britain and does not differentiate them much from older voters. It therefore appears that the culturalist 'Generation Woke' hypothesis tells us more about why young Britons are more likely to identify as far left than older voters than the materialist 'Generation Rent' argument. It is worth adding that income, employment status and marital status also do not predict leftism or Green voting.

Second, young people on the left are more likely to vote Green and less likely to vote Labour than older people on the left. This is related to young people's differing flavour of leftism (woke cultural attitudes, greater concern with cost of living, weaker support for taxes and spending) that they may associate more with Green than Labour. They have not been politically conscious for as long as older voters and are less likely to have formed an emotional bond with Labour. In addition, Labour may represent the status quo and thus be blamed more by young people for the country's problems. Finally, disproportionate young Green voting is not more related to the youthful charismatic appeal of Zack Polanski. Material factors top the concerns of young voters but this does not explain why young voters vote differently from older voters, which has more to do with culturally-inflected positional issues.

The implications of these findings for a future Westminster election is unclear. Young people are a smaller demographic with a lower propensity to turn out than older voters. The next election is likely to involve multiple 3-way or even 4-way local splits that voters will find it difficult to navigate. Despite a greater willingness of left voters to vote tactically to keep Reform out (compared to right voters willingness to vote tactically against Labour), uncertainty about which left party to switch to may limit Labour's advantage with left-wing tactical voters. On the right, Reform may emerge as the more clear right-wing leader, sending a stronger signal to Tory tactical voters keen on keeping Labour out.

Yet regardless of what happens at the next election, as zoomers and millennials become the median voter, the left tilt among voters under 35 will eventually make an impact nationwide. This more culturally progressive generation could transform British politics in a Canadian direction, paving the way for the dominance of a left

bloc which Labour may eventually be able to capture. That could change Britain's natural party of government from Conservative to Labour and/or reinforce a leftward policy shift on issues where the right currently has the advantage, such as immigration and culture wars. Unless Reform or the Tories address the meaning-making environment which frames politics - education, media and the ethos of institutions - they are likely to lose substantial political ground in the coming decades.

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